

A Study of Financial Literacy among the Tribal People

Dr. Narayan N. Gadhe

Professor and Head Dept. of Economics, Loknete Vyankatrao Hiray Arts, Science
& Commerce College, Nashik

Corresponding author- Dr. Narayan N. Gadhe

Email- narayangadhe123@ gmail.com

Abstract

Financial system plays a vital role in the economic progress of the country. In India, though 24 per cent youths are financially literate but most of tribal people are found to be financially illiterate. Due to the low literacy rate among them and low income level, they do not have sufficient knowledge of financial literacy. The present paper tries to find out the current situation of financial literacy among tribal people.

Key words: Financial Literacy, Tribal People

Introduction

Country's economic growth depends on financial literacy. There is a positive relation between the economic progress and financial literacy. In developed countries find the higher rate of financial literacy where as in a developing country like India find the lower rate of financial literacy. According to census 2011 the percentage of schedule tribe is 8.6 per cent¹. Most of the tribal people are illiterate. They are less financially literate than other Indian people. The present paper focuses on the financial literacy of tribal people.

Meaning of Financial Literacy

The illiterates of the twenty first century will not be those who cannot read and write but those who cannot learn, unlearn and relearn. Similarly, financial literate will not be those who know how to save but those who can achieve their financial goals and achieve financial freedom.² –

Alvin Toffler. Financial literacy means having the knowledge, skills, and confidence to make responsible financial decisions throughout your life – from how to spend your allowance – to saving for school, travel, or a home – to ultimately retire in comfort.³

Financial Literacy among India's neighboring countries

The most financially literate continent of the world is Australia, having 62.50% financial literacy among the adults, whereas Asia having only 32.29 percent financially literate adults. It is less than the Africa.⁴ The S & P report says in the BRICS countries as an average 28 per cent of adults were financially literate. It is greater than India's financial literacy rate.⁵

The following table shows the rates of financial literacy among India's neighboring countries

Table No.1 Financial Literacy among India's neighbor

Sr. No.	Country	Rate of Financial Literacy (%)
1	India	24
2	China	28
3	Pakistan	26
4	Bangladesh	19
5	Sri Lanka	35
6	Nepal	18
7	Myanmar	52

Source:

<https://www.counterview.net/2015/12/indias-financial-literacy-worse-than.html>

As per the latest survey by Standard & Poor has shown only 24 per cent adults in Indian are financially literate. The level of India's financial literacy is less than the neighboring countries like Pakistan and Sri Lanka. Pakistan's and Sri Lanka's adults financially literate rate were 26 per cent and 35 per cent respectively. Whereas Bangladesh's and Nepal's financial literacy rate were lower than India.

Objective of the study

The present study attempts to analyses the level of financial literacy of the respondents from the small

tribal village Rajewadi, Tal- Tryambakeshwar in Nashik district. It is also aim to study the comparative rate of Financial Literacy among India's neighbor.

Research Methodology

For the purpose of the study a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. For the convenience and easy to understand of the respondents the questionnaire prepared in Marathi language. All the information collected through personal interviews using the questions included in the questionnaire. The questionnaire covered some important dimensions like bank account operations, Prime-minister Jan-dhan accounts, saving and

investment, loans, life insurance policy, ATM cards

Sampling and data collection

The study was based on primary data as well as secondary data. Primary data was collected by convenience sampling method and secondary data collected through books, periodicals and internet. The sampling frame comprised respondents aged 18 years or above from the tribal village Rajewadi in

Survey Sample Profile

etc.

Nashik district. This study uses a sample of 99 respondents from the above said village. All the respondents were contacted directly by visit in their residences. The data collected were randomly selected and covered various variables like age group, educational level, income of the households etc.

Key Survey Results

1. The overall financial literacy is very low among the tribal people.
2. 83% respondents having bank accounts whereas 13% respondent have not bank accounts.
3. 60% respondent opened Prime-Mister Jan-dhan bank accounts and 40% were not opened such accounts.
4. 66% respondent having ATM cards whereas 34% respondents have not possessed ATM cards.
5. 80% respondent said that the PIN of ATM card was not share to anyone. 10% respondent said that PIN share to the relatives whereas 10% said that it could be share to friends.
6. 70% of respondent like to invest their money in gold or silver. Only 5% respondent invests money in mutual funds. Those who are serving in various places those are investing money in mutual funds.
7. Only 12% respondent borrowed loans whereas 88% were not taken loans from any sources.

8. Most of the respondents borrowed loans from money lenders.
9. Only 9% respondent purchased life insurance policy whereas 91% respondents haven't the LIC policy.
10. 72% respondent does not use online payment methods. Only 28% respondent use the online payment system.
11. Only 16% respondent prepared their annual family budget and 84% respondent does not prepared their family budget.
12. 91% respondent did not keep the record of their family income and expenditure.

References:

1. <https://tribal.nic.in/ST/Statistics8518.pdf>
2. <https://www.tflguide.com/are-you-a-financial-literate/>
3. Gary Rabbior, Money and Youth- A Guide to Financial literacy
4. <https://getmoneyrich.com/financial-literacy-data/>
5. <https://www.counterview.net/2015/12/indias-financial-literacy-worse-than.html>